

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 1.8 to AD4.1 – Withdrawal Form for Legal Guardians

WP 4

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PARC TASK 4.1.1 TEMPLATE

WITHDRAWAL FORM FOR LEGAL GUARDIANS

ON BEHALF OF PARTICIPANTS NOT ABLE TO GIVE CONSENT

INSTRUCTIONS ON HOW TO USE THIS TEMPLATE

This is a template, which can be used to develop a tailored certificate of informed consent for participants in PARC surveys, who are legally eligible to provide informed consent. According to GDPR, this applies to ages over 16.

To use this template, **change the red text** with wording appropriate for your study, and *delete all instructions and brackets in blue italicized text*. You may introduce further changes, as required by the study design and national requirements, while ensuring compliance with GDPR.

GDPR is Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), OJ L119, 4.5.2016, p. 1-88.

Encoding of task 4.1.1.1 templates

The encoding rules of templates in PARC: the templates are given an acronym, shown in the footer, which denotes type, version, year of revision and follows the key:

TYPE: CIC=Certificate of informed consent. TARGET AUDIENCE: AD = Adults. VERSION: V1 =Version No. DATE OF LAST REVISION: 2023-03-28

Participant Withdrawal Form for Legal Guardians

[title of study, e.g., PARC biomonitoring study on

exposure to [specify name of pollutant(s) or type of study [aligned study on ...]]

Dear legal guardian,

You and your child can withdraw from the *[name study]* at any time and without disclosing your reasons, by completing and signing this form. *[If applicable (for studies involving children / young people): This includes the possibility to withdraw data and samples collected in the past from a child, after consent of a parent / guardian, who has subsequently grown and may now express his/her own assent or dissent].* The form can be completed by you or by someone who is able to act on your behalf. Your signed consent and withdrawal forms will be kept by *[specify organization name]* as a record of your and your child's wishes. The options available to you for withdrawal are shown. Please indicate your preference by marking the appropriate box.

I wish to withdraw my child from the PARC study and request:
<input type="checkbox"/> NO FURTHER CONTACT BUT THE CODED ¹ SAMPLES OF MY CHILD AND INFORMATION OF ME AND MY CHILD CAN BE USED We will no longer be contacted but give our permission to <i>[Specify name of PARC partner organization carrying out the study]</i> to retain and use information and samples already provided by my child.
<input type="checkbox"/> NO FURTHER CONTACT AND THE SAMPLES OF MY CHILD AND INFORMATION OF ME AND MY CHILD <u>CANNOT</u> BE USED We will no longer be contacted by <i>[Specify organization name]</i> and the information and samples we already provided cannot be used for further analyses. My child's samples will be destroyed, but we understand that it may not be possible to trace all distributed samples remnants. We understand that it is not possible to remove coded data originating from my child from analyses that have already been completed. <i>[Specify organization name]</i> will only hold my information for audit purposes.

¹ The term "coded" means that my name has been replaced by a code, in order to protect your child's and your personal data.

ANNEX 1.8 – WITHDRAWAL FORM FOR LEGAL GUARDIANS

On behalf of the participant withdrawing from the PARC study:

Location and
date

Name of participant

Name and signature of the participant's legal
guardian

On behalf of *[Specify name of PARC partner organization carrying out the study]*:

Location and date

Name of PARC staff

Signature of PARC staff

For internal use only: Participant code _____

This template was adapted from the HBM4EU document available at www.hbm4eu.eu